

15/9/2021 Wednesday

9h - 9h30	MORNING BOOSTER
9h30 - 10h30	Lecture: Lean Startup and rapid prototyping
10h30 - 10h45	Break
10h45 - 16h	Workshop: Prototyping & Ideation
16h - 17h	Online Wrap - Up off the day
17h - ...	Workshop: Prototyping & Ideation continued

16/9/2021 Thursday

9h - 9h30	MORNING BOOSTER
9h30 - 10h	Lecture: Product validation & Testing
10h30 - 10h45	Break
10h15 - 16h	Workshop: Prototyping & Ideation
16h - 17h	Online Wrap - Up off the day
17h - ...	Workshop: Prototyping & Ideation continued

17/9/2021 Friday

9h - 9h30	MORNING BOOSTER
9h30 - 10h30	Pitch instructions
10h30 - 14h	Compile your results (submit Circularity Scan self evaluation) Breakout with industry partners (1h/team)
14h30 - 16h	Live Pitch Few slides on behalf of the company (what do we do + why did we submitted a challenge, 3-5min) + pitch by the participants
16h - 16h30	Jury moment
16h30	AWARD & WRAP UP